

Weekly Progress Report

Date: 16/11/2015 – 20/11/2015

Maximus Byamukama

Mary Nsabagwa

Emmanuel Kondela

Plans:

- Conclude and Submit Revision 4 of Evaluation Report

Activities:

- Revision 4 of the evaluation report was finished and uploaded.

Plans for next week

- Wait for Revision 4 Feedback
- Discuss high level titles for possible papers to be published individually and collectively
- Continue work on PhD proposals